

Role Of The Motivation And Anxiety In Learning English

Mehrdad Moradi, Mohammadreza Jamili

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Abstract

Motivation has an important role for the learners in language learning. On the other hand, the study about motivation and anxiety in learning language have not been discussed adequately. Motivation is a significant factor for engaging the EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students in their learning process. According to Dornyei (1998), "some researchers agree that motivation is answerable for determining human performance by stimulating it and giving it direction. Engaging learners' motivation could help them to have a way to achieve their dreams. On the other hand, English learning anxiety had little effect on English learning motivation for the dissimilar levels of language proficiency students, especially for students in the intermediate level. Communication is one of the elementary human nature. According to Levis (Lewis, Simons, & Fennig, 2014) English is the third most widely used languages in the world. So, English plays an important role to link with people all around the world. Gardner (1985) believes that learner's motivation has long been recognized as one of the key factors affecting English language learning. The study is a literature review to find the students' motivation in learning English. Students had both high integrative and instrumental motivation to learn English and determine how and to what extent foreign language learning motivation and anxiety interact with each other that influence English language learning performances.

Introduction

Literature review

1. Motivation

Motivation is a significant factor for engaging the EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students in their learning process. According to Dornyei (1998), "some researchers agree that motivation is answerable for determining human performance by stimulating it and giving it direction. Engaging learners' motivation could help them to have a way to achieve their dreams. Gardner (R. C. Gardner et al., 1985) indicated that motivation is "the amount to which the specific works or strives to learn the language because of a wish to do so and the approval experienced in the activity".

This study helps to understand students' motivation in learning English and help the faculty to enhance the students' motivation so they could be successful in their learning.

2. Integrative vs. Instrumental Motivation

According to Gardner (1985, as cited in Kitjaroonchai, 2012) in order to comprehend why language students were motivated, it was essential to understand the students' ultimate aim or purpose for learning the language. He referred to this as student's orientation. His theory of second language learning motivation was recognized in two distinct placements.

2.1. Integrative Motivation

An integrated motivation is to syndicate the language with the student target language. In integrative motivation, the students learn the target language so they could get better comprehends and to know people who speak up the language and mix up in their culture. According to Gardner and Masgoret (2003), Integrative motivation denotes to "an openness to recognize at least in part with another language community" (p.126). Along with that, Mun (2011) describes integrative motivation as a motivation without any external inducement (reward). As a result, an integrative motivation leads the learners to learn the foreign language due to the positive manners. Yet, the learners wish to integrate into the target language community.

2.2. Instrumental Motivation

Students with an instrumental motivation are students who want to learn a language because of some reasons such as job demands or getting into college. Gardner and Lambert

(1972) measured instrumental motivation as a means to get the social and economic reward through L2 Learning.

Motivation is an imperative factor in L2 learning. Some researcher also agrees that the mixture of integrative and instrumental motivation can involve the learner motivation in learning their target language. Also, Mun (2011) describes instrumental motivation as a motivation to study a language with more useful purposes, such as looking for jobs or reach higher social rank.

According to Wong-Fillmore (1991) there are three situations necessary for learning L2, such as:

- a) The need of motivated learners to learn the target language.
- b) Native presenter's support to learn L2.
- c) Interaction between a native speaker of the target language and students.

3. Intrinsic vs. Extrinsic Motivation

In this section, the other types of motivation clarified, they were intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Fundamentally, there was similarity between intrinsic/ extrinsic and integrative/ instrumental motivation. As a result, Rehman et al. (2014) classify intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, as follows:

3.1. Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation is a motivation which comes from the individual themselves. They want to acquire the target language because of their self-desire to study it. According to Woolfolk (Woolfolk, 1998) "intrinsic motivation is a motivation that stems from features such as interest or curiosity" (p.374). In relation to that, intrinsic motivation could happen when the student has an interest or interest in learning English without any pressure to learn it.

3.2. Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation is a motivation which comes from the situation. They want to learn the target language because it is the difficulties of their job or school. According to Harmer (2007), extrinsic motivation produced by outside reasons, such as, the need to pass an exam, the hope for financial reward, or the opportunity of future travel. Besides, Deci and Ryan (1985) propose 4 categories for extrinsic motivation. They were external regulation, interjection, identification, and integration.

Kitjaroonchai (2012) showed a study on students' motivation to learn English as a second language. The researcher tried to reproduce the study and adjust the questionnaire but using different sample which was the fresh year students at EDSWCU. In this study, Kitjaroonchai (2012) complicated 266 students from 10 different secondary and high schools in Education Service Area 4, Saraburi Province. The result of his study was the learners were highly motivated to learn English by having total mean score 4.39. In comparing the two types of learning motivation: integrative motivation and instrumental motivation, it was nearly a similar outcome among integrative and instrumental motivation to learn English with average mean scores of 4.22 and 4.51, respectively. Their instrumental motivation to learn English was very high and it slightly outperformed their integrative motivation by 0.29. These research findings were reliable with the previous studies by Wimolmas (2013).

A study by Wimolmas (2013) in Thailand expected to determine learners motivation in learning English, in term of instrumental and integrative motivation. Definitely, the researcher involved 30 first-year undergraduate learners at an international institute of engineering and technology. The result of his study showed that the learners were relatively highly motivated. Therefore, the researcher found that the learners were more instrumentally motivated to learn English.

Rehman et al. (2014) showed a study to discover the role of motivation in learning English for Pakistani students. The study involved 50 Pakistani intermediate learners from a private college. In relation to motivation, the result found that 70% of the learners were more instrumentally motivated to learn English. Otherwise, 24% students wanted to learn English because they love English (integrative motivation) and 6% students did not show their consent. Oxford and Shearin (1994) as cited in Dörnyei (1998) stated that “Quite possibly the cause of the motivation is very significant in a practical sense to instructors who want to encourage learners’ motivation. Without knowing where the roots of motivation lie, how can instructors water those roots?”

These statements could encourage the instructors to be the best role for the learners. Therefore, the learners could be interested to learn English more. Therefore, educators should pay attention to the learners to train and introduce the learners about the intrinsic motivation in order to develop their ability in using English as their second language. Gardner (1985) states that the integrative oriented students displayed more persistent and intense motivation rather than other students. They had strong desire to learn the language and hold positive attitudes toward English speaking people and toward learning English. Their interest in English would affect their learning and successes.

4. Language Anxiety

Language anxiety is the feelings of embarrassment and shame, being afraid of making mistakes and apprehension in speaking skill. Anxiety and fear are series of mind and body responses, which are practiced by each student, especially when they speak in front of the class. In many cases, students’ feeling of tension, worry or nervousness may prevent their language learning and speaking skill when speaking practice is happening. The students lately find the utterance I feel my heart beating very fast to face this speaking English language, the condition surely will be making their speaking in front of class. As Liu (C.-Y. Liu et al., 2020) believed, the association between anxiety and foreign language learning is generally reported to be negative. Though, the positive aspects of anxiety as far as foreign language learning have been discovered by other researchers (Azmi & Sham, 2018; Budin, 2014; Kleinmann, 1977; Safari Moghaddam & Ghafournia, 2019).

One of the most main difficulties students have to overcome in language classes is anxiety. Brown (2000) mentioned that this problem usually appears once speakers undertake their oral presentation to be wrong, stupid or inconceivable. Other researchers also confirmed that language learning anxiety is one of the most devastating factors to language learning process (Dörnyei, 2014; Ehrman, 1996; Öztekin, 2011; Yashima, MacIntyre, & Ikeda, 2018; Yen et al., 2012). According to Safari Moghaddam, most of the students had a feeling of pleasure and want to continue learning English. Though, a few of them were worried about forgetting vocabularies and grammar, and they felt nervous though they were going to speak in class. One learner claimed that learning English was very difficult at the beginning, but little by little, it got more interesting (Safari Moghaddam & Ghafournia, 2019).

5. The Relationship between Language Learning Anxiety and motivation

Most of the students were prone to instrumental rather than integrative motivation in terms of learning English, and their levels of English language class anxiety were higher than their levels of English use and test anxiety. The findings can help explain the nature of both English learning anxiety and English learning motivation as psychological constructs to learners. Based on the explanation above, the researcher achieves that there is a close association between anxiety and motivation in speaking activity. Because when learners have a low level of anxiety, then the student will be more motivated in learning while learners with high levels of anxiety have less motivation in learning.

Some studies regarding the connection between language motivation and anxiety in language learning have drawn the interest of several researchers. For example, Gardner, Day, and MacIntyre (1991) mentioned that interactively motivated students “are less nervous in L2 contexts” (p.212) than learners who are instrumentally motivated. Their findings indicate that anxiety and motivation are “two separate dimensions with overlapping behavioral consequences” (p.212). Noels et al. (1999) stated “the more students feel motivated, the less effort they will expend and the more anxiety they will feel” (p.31). In the view of Brown, Robson, and Rosenkjar (2001) learners’ motivation and anxiety were negatively correlated and a lack of motivation could cause anxious behaviors. Further, Liu (2020) found that the students’ motivation was positively correlated with their English proficiency. An interesting negative correlation between second and foreign language learning anxiety and achievement is also addressed in the studies (Aida, 1994; Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986). Empirical research

has shown that the more anxious foreign languages students are, the less willing they are to get involved in learning activities, and thus to have lower performance results than those who are less-anxious students (1994).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the impact that anxiety has on English learning motivation with regard to gender is undeniable.

We can conclude that the integrative students' motivation was not as big as their instrumental motivation which means the motivation of learning English could be affected by their environment (Al-Bustan & Al-Bustan, 2009). Students were able to realize the importance of learning English. Students thought that by learning English they will be able to speak with native English speaking country; to find a good job in the future; help them while traveling abroad.

In general, instrumental motivation plays an important role in English learning motivation to English-majoring students, whereas, integrative motivation plays a significant part in English learning motivation to non-English-majoring students. Interestingly, whether looking at English-majoring or non-English-majoring students, the results show that English class anxieties are at a higher level than English use and test anxiety. The findings of this study are consistent with Huang's (2001) statements. Huang (2001) noted that English language instruction in Taiwan focused on more teacher-centered practices rather than student-centered practices. Based on this, some students are anxious because they are under a lot of pressure, and so they lack motivation to learn English in class and anxiety only had a slight effect on English learning motivation of the intermediate group.

The researcher wants to give some suggestion to the teachers and students who are teaching and learning English as their second language. Hopefully, by giving these suggestions, the teachers and the students could improve their English learning and their style in teaching EFL. First, the suggestion for the students such as students need to set their goal; take part in activity group and show interest in learning English. Next, the suggestions to the teachers such as teacher ought to use activity and method which gain the students creativity and interest such as making a pair assignment or using songs or movies to teach EFL; should create cooperative classroom atmosphere to lighten students' anxiety; and not only perfect in English but also good at managing the students.

In order to reduce learners' anxiety and increase their learning motivation, instructors might also take the affective learning atmosphere into consideration. In a learning environment where learners can learn without pressure and stress, they may display positive motivation and low anxiety in the classroom. Language teachers need some special in-service training courses on general psychology, including language anxiety in order to deal with the students' feeling of stress and anxiety in their classes. Effective teacher training courses can help language teachers learn the students' potential sources of negative language-learning anxiety and the effective ways to cope with them (Safari Moghaddam & Ghafournia, 2019).

To reduce language learning anxiety, Horwitz, et, al (1986) noted that educators should help anxious students to deal with existing anxiety-provoking situations and endeavor to make the learning context less stressful. Creating a low-anxiety classroom atmosphere is clearly a vital prerequisite to language learning success. Language classrooms are an "inherently face-threatening environment" (Dörnyei, 2014; Dörnyei & Clément, 2001) as learners are expected to communicate using a "severely restricted language code" (p.91). Therefore, instructors should encourage students to recognize their language anxieties and fears and offer some strategies to overcome them. In the long run, teachers can help students by reducing negativity of learning English, raising students' self-belief and assisting them in alleviating the anxiety caused by expectations of failure.

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Author Information

Mehrdad Moradi

Department of English, Neyshabur Branch, Islamic Azad University, Neyshabur, Iran

Mohammadreza Jamili

Department of English, Neyshabur Branch, Islamic Azad University, Neyshabur, Iran
